

The Taxonomic Report

OF THE INTERNATIONAL LEPIDOPTERA SURVEY

ISSN 2643-4776 (print) / ISSN 2643-4806 (online)

Checklist of the butterflies of Rhode Island

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ABSTRACT. In preparation for a book on Rhode Island butterflies, the current paper lists all species documented in the Ocean State with their county distribution, and early/late flight dates.

Additional key words: spring flight, summer flight.

INTRODUCTION

Having moved to Rhode Island in 1983, I contacted author Paul Opler and inquired which butterflies I might encounter in the state. Opler sent me a checklist in the form of a spreadsheet, which indicated a mere six species of butterflies recorded in the state. I immediately embarked on an intensive 2-year survey of Rhode Island butterflies, continuing through 1984. Interestingly, there was only one other lepidopterist at the time, Jack Friedel, who's data is incorporated into the survey. After moving out of Rhode Island, I continued annual spring and summer trips back to the state, for several years, then occasional trips to "blockbust" towns missing certain butterfly records. My subsequent contact with other Rhode Island lepidopterists was with Joanne Michaud and Rick Enser of The Nature Conservancy, who were surveying Rhode Island butterflies as well. Their data is also incorporated here. Over time, I managed to make contact with many other "butterfliers" with whom I established a reporting network. Martin Wencek, Clare Stone and family produced an enormous number of records almost daily since 1992 to the present. To increase interest in butterflies, I established the Ocean State Butterflies Yahoo Group in 2008, which functioned for several years and generated a large amount of data, in particular from contributions of Walter Bosse, who observed butterflies almost daily during the warm season. Subsequently, the Rhode Island Butterflies and Moths Facebook Group continued to produce photographic records from many contributors. More recently, the iNaturalist and e-Butterfly platforms have gained dominance on the internet, producing a very large number of verifiable records. The result is this checklist, current to 2024.

Fig. 1. *Argynnis idalia*, Charlestown, R.I., July 28, 1984. Photo by H. Pavulaan. Last observed in Rhode Island in 1991 (three observations).

CHECKLIST

Key:

Latin names follow Pelham (2023) with several minor changes. Common names follow the NABA (accessed online 2024) with several minor changes. Status indicates presence in Rhode Island, followed by counties in which each species was recorded. Counties are annotated as follows:

BRI = Bristol
KEN = Kent
NEW = Newport
PRO = Providence
WAS = Washington.

Lastly, early/late dates are indicated.

PAPILIONIDAE (Swallowtails)

Eurytides marcellus marcellus (Zebra Swallowtail): Stray. KEN, PRO, WAS. June 20-July 19 (but one unspecified date in August).

Battus philenor philenor (Pipevine Swallowtail): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. May 14-October 19.

Papilio polyxenes asterius (Black Swallowtail): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. April 3-October 15.

Heraclides cresphontes (Giant Swallowtail): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. July 14-September 17.

Pterourus troilus troilus (Spicebush Swallowtail): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. May 3-October 8.

Pterourus palamedes palamedes (Palamedes Swallowtail): Stray. WAS. June 12.

Pterourus glaucus glaucus (Eastern Tiger Swallowtail): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. March 20-October 5

Pterourus canadensis (Canadian Tiger Swallowtail): Stray. KEN, WAS. April 18-July 9.

Pterourus bjorkae (New England Tiger Swallowtail (or) Bjork's Tiger Swallowtail): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. May 2-June 21. Recently described in The Taxonomic Report (Pavulaan, 2024) (**Figs. 2-3**).

Pterourus new species (Mid-summer Tiger Swallowtail): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. June 29-September 12. Undescribed sibling species, proposed as a potential new species (Wang, 2017; Schmidt, 2020) (**Figs. 4-5**).

PIERIDAE (Whites and Sulphurs)

Pyrisitia lisa lisa (Little Yellow): Stray, seasonal breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. May 14-October 12.

Abaeis nicippe (Sleepy Orange): Stray, seasonal breeding resident. WAS. July 28-September 25.

Colias philodice (Clouded Sulphur): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. April 10-November 27.

Colias eurytheme (Orange Sulphur): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. April 13-December 17.

Phoebis sennae eubule (Cloudless Sulphur): Stray, seasonal breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. June 24-October 24.

Phoebis philea philea (Orange-barred Sulphur): Historic stray. KEN. August 15.

Phoebis agarithe maxima (Large Orange Sulphur): Historic stray. PRO, WAS. August 26-September 17.

Anthocharis midea annickae (Falcate Orangetip): Historic stray. WAS. (Date unknown).

Pontia protodice (Checkered White): Stray, vagrant breeding resident. KEN, PRO, WAS. August 10-October 12.

Pieris rapae rapae (Cabbage White): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. March 15-November 19.

Pieris brassicae brassicae (Large White): Historic accidental. "Rhode Island". (Date unknown).

Pieris oleracea oleracea (Mustard White): Historic record. NEW. (Date unknown).

LYCAENIDAE (Gossamer-wing Butterflies)

- Feniseca tarquinius tarquinius* (Harvester): Breeding resident. KEN, PRO, WAS. May 2-September 2.
- Lycaena hypophlaeas hypophlaeas* (American Copper): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. March 31-November 3.
- Tharsalea hyllus* (Bronze Copper): Historic resident. PRO, WAS. June 23-October 2.
- Tharsalea epixanthe epixanthe* (Bog Copper): Breeding resident. KEN, PRO, WAS. June 20-July 26.
- Callophrys gryneus gryneus* (Olive Juniper Hairstreak): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. April 8-August 13.
- Callophrys hesseli hesseli* (Hessel's Hairstreak): Breeding resident. KEN, PRO, WAS. April 29-July 31.
- Callophrys niphon clarki* (Eastern Pine Elfin): Breeding resident. KEN, PRO, WAS. April 8-June 17.
- Callophrys irus irus* (Frosted Elfin): Breeding resident. KEN, PRO, WAS. April 25-June 20.
- Callophrys henrici henrici* (Henry's Elfin): Breeding resident. KEN, NEW, WAS. April 25-June 4.
- Callophrys polios polios* (Hoary Elfin): Breeding resident. KEN, PRO, WAS. April 14-June 12.
- Callophrys augustinus croesioides* (Brown Elfin): Breeding resident. KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. April 14-June 25.
- Satyrrium titus winteri* (Coral Hairstreak): Breeding resident. KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. June 28-August 22 (but one unspecified date in September).
- Satyrrium favonius ontario* (Northern Hairstreak): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, PRO, WAS. June 19-July 09.
- Satyrrium liparops strigosa* (Striped Hairstreak): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. June 30-August 15.
- Satyrrium caryaevorus* (Hickory Hairstreak): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, PRO, WAS. June 19-July 16.
- Satyrrium calanus falacer* (Banded Hairstreak): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. June 17-August 24.
- Satyrrium edwardsii edwardsii* (Edwards' Hairstreak): Breeding resident. KEN, PRO, WAS. June 25-August 6.
- Satyrrium acadica acadica* (Acadian Hairstreak): Breeding resident. KEN, PRO, WAS. July 2-July 17.
- Strymon melinus humuli* (Gray Hairstreak): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. April 25-October 11.
- Calycopis cecrops* (Red-banded Hairstreak): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. May 19-October 19.

Parrhasius m-album (White-M Hairstreak): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. April 23-October 4.

Glaucopsyche lygdamus couperi (Silvery Blue): Unknown status. KEN. June 5.

Celastrina lucia lucia (Northern Azure): Breeding resident. KEN.

Celastrina ladon (Spring Azure): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. March 20-June 4.

Celastrina serotina (Cherry Gall Azure): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. April 18-June 18.

Celastrina neglecta (Summer Azure): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. June 8-October 6.

Cupido comyntas comyntas (Eastern Tailed Blue): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. April 13-October 19.

NYMPHALIDAE (Brush-foot Butterflies)

Libytheana carinenta bachmanii (American Snout): Stray, seasonal breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. June 19-September 4.

Danaus plexippus plexippus (Monarch): Seasonal breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. April 28-December 1.

Danaus gilippus berenice (Queen): Stray. NEW, WAS. June 24-August 4.

Heliconius charithonia tuckeri (Zebra Longwing): Accidental. PRO. September 6.

Dione incarnata nigrior (Gulf Fritillary): Stray. WAS. August 19-October 22.

Euptoieta claudia (Variegated Fritillary): Seasonal breeding resident. KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. June 10-October 20.

Boloria bellona bellona (Meadow Fritillary): Breeding resident. NEW, PRO, WAS. May 26-August 16.

Boloria myrina myrina (Silver-bordered Fritillary): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. May 20-September 22.

Argynnis idalia idalia (Regal Fritillary): Historic. KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. June 15-September 5. (Fig. 1).

Argynnis diana (Diana Fritillary): Accidental. NEW. June 22.

Argynnis cybele cybele (Great Spangled Fritillary): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. May 25-October 6.

Argynnis aphrodite aphrodite (Aphrodite Fritillary): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, PRO, WAS. June 19-August 17.

Argynnis atlantis atlantis (Atlantis Fritillary): Historic. PRO. (Dates unknown).

Limenitis archippus archippus (Viceroy): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. May 26-October 12.

Limenitis arthemis arthemis (White Admiral): Breeding resident. KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. June 7-September 15.

Limenitis arthemis astyanax (Red-spotted Purple): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. May 20-September 28.

Asterocampa celtis celtis (Hackberry Emperor): Breeding resident. BRI, PRO, WAS. July 10-September 25.

Asterocampa clyton clyton (Tawny Emperor): Breeding resident. BRI, PRO. July 8-July 27.

Aglais milberti milberti (Milbert's Tortoiseshell): Breeding resident. BRI, NEW, PRO, WAS. April 14-November 7 (Population hibernates).

Nymphalis l-album j-album (Compton Tortoiseshell): Breeding resident. KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. March 20-September 7 (Population hibernates).

Nymphalis antiopa lintnerii (Mourning Cloak): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. February 26-November 30. (Part of population hibernates, part migrates south).

Nymphalis interrogationis (Question Mark): Breeding resident and seasonal migrant. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. March 10-December 4 (Part of population hibernates, part migrates south).

Nymphalis comma (Eastern Comma): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. March 3-December 3 (Population hibernates).

Nymphalis progne (Gray Comma): Historic. PRO. (Date unknown).

Nymphalis faunus faunus (Green Comma): Historic. PRO. (Date unknown).

Vanessa virginiensis (American Lady): Seasonal migrant, temporary breeding. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. March 20-November 22.

Vanessa cardui (Painted Lady): Seasonal migrant, temporary breeding. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. April 8-December 26.

Vanessa atalanta rubria (Red Admiral): Seasonal migrant, temporary breeding. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. April 2-November 13.

Junonia coenia coenia (Common Buckeye): Seasonal migrant, temporary breeding. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. May 11-November 21.

Euphydryas phaeton phaeton (Baltimore): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. June 7-July 25.

Chlosyne nycteis nycteis (Silvery Checkerspot): Breeding resident. BRI. June 14.

Chlosyne harrisii harrisii (Harris' Checkerspot): Breeding resident. BRI. June 9-June 29.

Phyciodes tharos tharos (Pearl Crescent): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. May 5-October 26.

Phyciodes sp. near-cocyta (Northern Crescent): Breeding resident. KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. May 25-August 7.

Anaea andria (Goatweed Leafwing): Accidental or Stray. WAS. August 25.

Coenonympha californica inornata (Inornate Ringlet): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. May 9-October 27.

Lethe anthedon anthedon (Northern Pearly Eye): Breeding resident. KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. June 16-September 9.

Lethe eurydice eurydice (Eyed Brown): Breeding resident. WAS. July 4-July 12.

Lethe appalachia appalachia (Appalachian Brown): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. June 5-September 17.

Megisto cymela [summer flight] (Little Wood Satyr): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. June 23-August 13.

Megisto viola [spring flight] (Viola's Wood Satyr): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. May 4-July 5.

Cercyonis pegala alope (Common Wood Nymph): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. June 25-October 8.

HESPERIIDAE (Skippers)

Cecropterus lyciades (Hoary Edge): Breeding resident. KEN, PRO, WAS. June 3-July 14.

Cecropterus bathyllus (Southern Cloudywing): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, PRO, WAS. May 2-July 14.

Cecropterus pylades pylades (Northern Cloudywing): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, PRO, WAS. May 21-July 30.

Urbanus proteus proteus (Long-tailed Skipper): Seasonal migrant. NEW, WAS. August 18-October 5.

Epargyreus clarus clarus (Silver-spotted Skipper): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. May 12-October 4.

Pholisora catullus (Common Sootywing): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. April 28-September 16.

Burnsius communis (Common Checkered Skipper): Stray. WAS. July 28-September 15.

Erynnis icelus (Dreamy Duskywing): Breeding resident. KEN, PRO, WAS. May 1-June 30.

Erynnis brizo (Sleepy Duskywing): Breeding resident. KEN, PRO, WAS. April 20-June 16.

Gesta martialis (Mottled Duskywing): Historic. WAS. May 13 (one undated specimen from July).

Gesta juvenalis juvenalis (Juvenal's Duskywing): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. April 13-June 27.

Gesta horatius (Horace's Duskywing): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. May 2-September 15 (one undated report from April).

Gesta funeralis (Funereal Duskywing): Stray. WAS. September 25.

Gesta baptisiae (Wild Indigo Duskywing): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. April 16-September 27.

Gesta lucilius (Columbine Duskywing): Historic. PRO. July 19-August 16 (one undated specimen from May).

Gesta persius persius (Persius Duskywing): Historic. BRI, WAS. May 9-May 28.

Euphyes dion (Dion Skipper): Stray. KEN, WAS. July 22.

Euphyes conspicua orono (Black Dash): Breeding resident. KEN, PRO, WAS. July 7-August 4.

Euphyes bimacula bimacula (Two-spotted Skipper): Historic. PRO, KEN. July 1-July 22.

Euphyes vestris metacomet (Dun Skipper): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. June 4-September 5.

Anatrytone logan logan (Delaware Skipper): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. May 23-August 19.

Hylephila phyleus phyleus (Fiery Skipper): Seasonal migrant. NEW, PRO, WAS. July 28-October 21.

Limochores origenes origenes (Crossline Skipper): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. May 23-October 6.

Limochores mystic mystic (Long Dash): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. May 27-September 14.

Polites themistocles themistocles (Tawny-edged Skipper): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. May 19-October 11.

Polites coras coras (Tawny-edged Skipper): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. May 17-October 17.

Polites egeremet (Northern Broken Dash): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. June 2-September 7.

Vernia verna (Little Glassywing): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. June 4-September 19.

Atalopedes huron (Huron Sachem): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. May 15-October 26.

- Hesperia leonardus leonardus* (Leonard's Skipper): Breeding resident. KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. August 6-September 21.
- Hesperia metea metea* (Cobweb Skipper): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. April 12-June 19.
- Hesperia sassacus sassacus* (Indian Skipper): Breeding resident. KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. May 14-July 23.
- Poanes massasoit massasoit* (Mulberry Wing): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. July 6-August 7.
- Poanes viator zizaniae* (Broad-winged Skipper): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. July 1-September 19.
- Lon hobomok hobomok* (Hobomok Skipper): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. May 22-July 17.
- Lon zabulon* (Zabulon Skipper): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. May 6-October 8.
- Atrytonopsis hianna hianna* (Dusted Skipper): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. May 15-July 14.
- Amblyscirtes hegon* (Pepper and Salt Skipper): Breeding resident. PRO, WAS. May 25-June 17.
- Amblyscirtes vialis* (Common Roadside Skipper): Breeding resident. KEN, PRO. June 3-June 6.
- Nastra lherminier* (Swarthy Skipper): Status uncertain. WAS. June 27-September 8.
- Lerema accius* (Clouded Skipper): Seasonal migrant. KEN, PRO, WAS. September 11-October 21.
- Thymelicus lineola lineola* (European Skipper): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. May 28-August 25.
- Panoquina panoquin* (Salt Marsh Skipper): Status uncertain. WAS. July 9.
- Panoquina ocola* (Ocola Skipper): Seasonal migrant. KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. August 28-October 11.
- Ancyloxypha numitor* (Least Skipper): Breeding resident. BRI, KEN, NEW, PRO, WAS. May 25-October 16.
- Calpododes ethlius* (Brazilian Skipper): Historic. "Rhode Island". (Undated specimen).

Fig. 2. *P. bjorkae*. Female. May 15, 1990. Great Swamp Management Area, West Kingston, Washington Co., R.I.

Fig. 3. *P. bjorkae*. Male. June 3, 1984. Great Swamp Management Area, West Kingston, Washington Co., R.I.

Fig. 4. "Mid-summer Tiger Swallowtail". Female. August 1, 1984. Great Swamp Management Area, West Kingston, Washington Co., R.I.

Fig. 5. "Mid-summer Tiger Swallowtail". Male. July 12, 2008. Newbury, Essex Co., MA.

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